

EOSC-IF

AI/ML

Recommender

System

Interoperability

Guideline

The EOSC Future project is co-funded by the European Union Horizon Programme call INFRAEOSC-03-2020, Grant Agreement number 101017536

Version 1.0

July 2023

EOSC-IF / AI/ML Recommender System

Interoperability Guideline

Lead by **PSNC**

Authored by Marcin Wolski (PSNC), Krzysztof Martyn (PSNC), Maciej Łabędzki (PSNC), Michail Xydas (Athena), Themis Zamani (GRNET), Bartosz Walter (PSNC), John Shepherdson (CESSDA), Michal Kolomanski (Cyfronet), Nikolaos Triantafyllis (GRNet)

Reviewed by Aggelikki Gkamiliari (Athena), George Papastefanatos (Athena), Thanassis Mantes (Athena), Pavel Weber (KIT)

Dissemination Level of the Document

Public

Document Identifier

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7849178>

Abstract

This document describes the current architecture of the EOSC Recommendation System and provides guidelines for three integration options with external service components.

Version History

Version	Date	Authors/Contributors	Description
Vo.1	20/04/2023	Marcin Wolski (PSNC), Krzysztof Martyn (PSNC), Maciej Łabędzki (PSNC), Michail Xydas (Athena), Themis Zamani (GRNET), Bartosz Walter (PSNC), John Shepherdson (CESSDA), Michal Kolomanski (Cyfronet), Nikolaos Triantafyllis (GRNet)	First draft
Vo.2	21/04/2023	Raimundas Tuminauskas (PSNC)	Review, minor corrections
Vo.3	21/04/2023	John Shepherdson (CESSDA)	Updated and submitted to EIAC
Vo.4	07/06/2023	John Shepherdson (CESSDA), Marcin Wolski (PSNC), Krzysztof Martyn (PSNC), Maciej Łabędzki (PSNC), Michal Kolomanski (Cyfronet),	Responded to substantive review comments
V1.0	18/07/2023	Marcin Wolski (PSNC), Krzysztof Martyn (PSNC), Maciej Łabędzki (PSNC), Michail Xydas (Athena), Themis Zamani (GRNET), Bartosz Walter (PSNC), John Shepherdson (CESSDA), Michal Kolomanski (Cyfronet), Nikolaos Triantafyllis (GRNet)	Final Version, uploaded to Zenodo

Copyright Notice

This work by Parties of the EOSC Future Consortium is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/). The EOSC Future project is co-funded by the European Union Horizon Programme call INFRAEOSC-03-2020, Grant Agreement number 101017536.

Table of Contents

Glossary	4
List of Abbreviations	5
1 Intended Audience	6
2 Description and main features	6
3 Response to Community Need	6
4 High-level Service Architecture.....	7
4.1 Evaluation framework	8
5 Definitions	9
6 Licensing Information	9
7 Related Guidelines	9
8 Adopted Standards	9
9 Integration Options	10
10 Interoperability Guidelines	10
10.1 Scenario 1 – adding a new client.....	11
10.1.1 Integration with RS Facade.....	11
10.1.2 Integration with the Databus.....	11
10.2 Scenario 2: adding a new recommendation engine	12
10.2.1 Step 1: Integration with data sources.....	12
10.2.1.1 Information available from the Search Service	12
10.2.1.2 Information available from the databus.....	13
10.2.1.3 Information available from internal databases	13
10.2.2 Step 2: Integration with the Facade	13
10.3 Evaluating a new integration	13
11 Examples of solutions implementing this specification	13
11.1 Scenario 1 example	13
11.2 Scenario 2 example.....	14
11.3 Scenario 3 example.....	14
12 Appendix A – RS Facade.....	15
12.1 RS Façade Endpoints	15
12.1.1 Recommendations endpoint	15
12.1.2 Response from connected recommendation engines	17
12.1.3 Project completion endpoint	18
12.1.4 Similar services endpoint.....	18
12.1.5 Similar resources endpoint	19
12.1.6 Databus messages.....	19
12.1.7 Example of request body for commendations endpoint.....	20
12.1.8 Example of request body for project completion endpoint:	21
12.1.9 Example of request body for similar services endpoint:.....	21
12.1.10 Example of request body for similar resources endpoint:	21
13 Appendix B – Databus.....	21
13.1 Databus messages	21
13.1.1 Marketplace database events	21

13.1.1.1	Create new user	21
13.1.1.2	Update user	21
13.1.1.3	Update service	22
13.1.1.4	Update ScientificDomain	22
13.2	Recommendations.....	22
13.2.1	Examples.....	23
	For a query for one resource type:	23
	For a query for all resource types:	23
References.....		27

Table of Tables

Table 7-1:	Related Guidelines.....	9
Table 8-1:	Adopted Standards	10
Table 10-1:	EOSC-RS integration points	10
Table 12-1:	Recommendation context	16
Table 12-2:	Recommendation candidates.....	16
Table 12-3:	Recommendation SearchData.....	16
Table 12-4:	Recommendation response.....	17
Table 12-5:	RecommendationSet	17
Table 12-6:	Databus message	17
Table 12-7:	Recommendation source.....	18
Table 12-8:	Project completion recommendation request	18
Table 12-9:	Project completion recommendation response	18
Table 12-10:	Similar services recommendation request	18
Table 12-11:	Similar services recommendation response	18
Table 12-12:	Similar resource suggestion request	19
Table 12-13:	RS Facade databus message - recommendations received.....	19
Table 12-14:	RS Facade databus message – recommendation source details	19
Table 13-1:	Recommendations message sent by RS Facade to Databus.....	22
Table 13-2:	Recommendation Context.....	22
Table 13-3:	Recommendation source	23

Table of Figures

Figure 4.1:	EOSC-RS high-level architecture	8
Figure 4.2:	Recommender Metrics Framework architecture	9
Figure 10.1:	integration points for a new EOSC-RS client	11
Figure 10.2:	integrating a new data source with the EOSC-RS	12
Figure 12.1:	RS Facade general scheme of operation	15

Glossary

EOSC Future project Glossary is incorporated by reference: <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/x/JOCK>

List of Abbreviations

Acronym	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface
EOSC-RS	EOSC Recommender System
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JSON-LD	JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data
REST	Representational state transfer
UI	User Interface

1 Intended Audience

The intended audience for the AI/ML Recommender System Interoperability Guideline is technical experts who would like to learn how to design their services to be interoperable or to integrate with the EOSC Recommender System (EOSC-RS) and/or who would like their resources (data sets) to be integrated within the EOSC-RS architecture.

It is also useful for software engineers who would like to design and develop recommendation engines to be integrated within the EOSC-RS architecture.

2 Description and main features

The EOSC-RS delivers two main types of recommendations: recommendations for Consumers (researchers) and recommendation for (resource) Providers. The former consist of three or fewer items in a 'Resources selected for you' panel. The later consist of auto-completion suggestions and/or statistics relating to the take-up of their services, based on recommendations made to Consumers.

The EOSC-RS is available to other EOSC Core Services through a dedicated API (the RS Facade), but it doesn't communicate with Consumers and Providers directly, instead various clients (such as the User Dashboard, the Search Service) present the information.

Use cases for Consumers focus on delivering recommendations based on various sources of information, in a way that makes it most useful to the users. The generated recommendations need to be closely related to the user's implied interests. Specifically, the following use cases are delivered to authenticated Consumers:

- Recommendations based on the user's history of viewing and ordering specific EOSC resources. The difference in the recommendations provided is directly related to the level of engagement of the user.
- Recommendations based on general popularity of an item among users. This use case is available also to non-authenticated users.
- Recommendations based on the popularity of an item among similar users. In this case, similarities between the current user and other users is the basis for generating recommendations.
- Recommendations based on similar services, i.e., delivering similar functions. Users may be interested in other services with a similar function to the one selected.

Additionally, the EOSC-RS can intersect existing features. For example, results returned by the Search Service could be re-ordered to match more closely the estimated user preferences. Moreover, users can provide feedback on the recommendations, which refines the preference model of the user and makes future recommendations more personal.

Providers constitute a separate viewpoint on the EOSC Portal, and they need a different set of recommendations than Consumers. Specifically, Providers receive:

- Guidance concerning onboarding new EOSC Products through auto-completion suggestions of specific fields.
- Feedback on the performance of their onboarded services through statistics relating to recommendations made and accepted.

Recommendations for researchers are provided by EOSC-RS via the Search Service or User Dashboard while recommendations and statistics for service Providers are gathered directly from EOSC-RS by the Provider Dashboard and displayed there.

3 Response to Community Need

Researchers (aka Consumers) constitute the majority of users of the EOSC Portal. The Front-Office requirements study [1] divides Researchers into several groups with respect to their expectations, needs and explicit requirements: senior scientists, chief scientists and doctoral and post-doc researchers. A clear majority of the requirements comes from the natural sciences domain which probably comprise ~50 percent of the set established for requirement gathering. However, the distribution of answers in relation to the particular scientific discipline has not become apparent during the analysis of the user requirements.

The estimated size of the target population of the EOSC is roughly 2 million, including 1.7 million researchers covering all major fields of science and all levels of seniority.

The motivation for enhancing the EOSC Portal with recommendations is based upon observed facts about challenges and pain points that Researchers usually meet during their typical work loads. Time is the most crucial factor relevant to all profiles of the researchers. Therefore, any functionality that facilitate shortening the duration of any step of the research process will provide significant improvements for the target users. Moreover, data access and findability have been indicated as the challenges that are directly related to the quality of research undertaken. Any feature facilitating seamless access to data, such as relevant recommendations, will improve scientific processes, ensuring higher quality research in less time, and could result in more publications of higher quality.

From the user perspective, relevant recommendations can help to improve overall user satisfaction within a web site. For example, a user who receives relevant service recommendations will be more satisfied with the experience and is more likely to use the site again and produce higher sales volumes [2]. This can improve user loyalty and further increase the perceived value of the site. At the provider end, the recommendation process can provide insights into the needs of the user and guide further customisation of the user experience. Finally, providing the user with an explanation for why a particular item is recommended is often as useful as the recommendation itself. For example, recommendations generated from observing a user's behaviour on the web site could be substantially different from the ones that use information about the selected content or relationships with other users with similar interests.

4 High-level Service Architecture

The components of the EOSC system with which EOSC-RS interacts are shown in Figure 4.1 and described below.

- **EOSC Portal** - the main website of the EOSC system offering a wide range of functionalities to end users. On the **Catalogue and Marketplace** page, among other things, researchers can search and order resources or create projects. The **User Dashboard** allows them to manage the user's profile and interact with the system in a personalised way. The **Knowledge Hub** provides a set of learning and training materials needed to effectively use the services available within EOSC. The **Provider Dashboard** is used by Providers to add and then manage the resources they provide to the EOSC system.
- **Search Service** - module for searching and browsing for resources and services in the EOSC system.
- **Databus** - message queue used to distribute events occurring in the system, among others, messages regarding the user's behaviour or events about adding new services to the system.
- **EOSC Monitoring** - part of the system, responsible for monitoring the operation of components.
- **EOSC Research Graph** - graph containing scientific resources, including publications, data sets offered within the EOSC system. Contains a subset of the OpenAIRE research graph contents.

Figure 4.1: EOSC-RS high-level architecture

Data sources containing large amounts of data that are static or do not change frequently (e.g EOSC Research Graph) are loaded directly into the Search Service. From there, they are sent to EOSC-RS. On the other hand, all dynamic and frequently changing data, such as User Actions, are distributed throughout the system via the Databus from where they are downloaded and processed by the appropriate EOSC-RS modules.

4.1 Evaluation framework

The Recommender Metrics Framework is an independent 'metrics framework as a service' used to support the evaluation and adaptation of recommendation mechanisms. Measuring the success of such systems is crucial to get valuable insights in many aspects that affect the user experience. The use of additional diagnostic metrics and visualizations, offers deeper and sometimes surprising insights into a model's performance. The evaluation is performed quantitatively (by processing information such as resources, user actions, ratings, and recommendations) in order to measure the impact of the AI-enhanced services and user satisfaction, as well as to incorporate this feedback and improve the services provided, via a user-friendly API and dashboard UI.

It consists of the following independent components, as shown in Figure 4.2:

- A Preprocessor that performs:
 - data retrieval through a connector module that claims and transforms data from various sources
 - service-associated knowledge correlations
 - dummy or dissociated data removal
 - tagging of various associations in the data
 - generation of statistics information.
- RSmetrics, responsible for:
 - processing the data
 - computing the metrics
 - producing the necessary information in a homogenized manner.

- A REST API, to allow clients to communicate with the metrics component
- A rich UI/dashboard, to display evaluation results.

Figure 4.2: Recommender Metrics Framework architecture

Some of the main features of the Recommender Metrics Framework:

- It supports multiple resources, multiple recommendation systems
- It supports date ranges
- It currently delivers the following Metrics: Catalog Coverage, Diversity Gini Index, Diversity Shannon Entropy, Novelty, User Coverage, Accuracy
- List of KPIs indicating measurable values that demonstrate how effectively key business objectives are achieved. It currently delivers the following KPIs metrics: Click-Through Rate, Hit Rate, Top 5 ordered Services, Top 5 recommended Services, Top 5 categories for recommendations, Top 5 categories for orders, Top 5 domains for orders, Top 5 domains for recommendations
- In the Graphs section, it exposes information graphs concerning attributes defined in the EOSC-RS, monthly user actions and recommendations.

5 Definitions

Any specialist terms used in this document are defined in context.

6 Licensing Information

All software components of the EOSC-RS are covered by an Open Source licence that is approved by the Open Source Initiative [3].

7 Related Guidelines

Table 7-1: Related Guidelines

Resource Type	Title	Short Description	relatedIdentifier
None			

8 Adopted Standards

The standards adopted are detailed in Table 8-1.

Table 8-1: Adopted Standards

Resource Type	Title	Short Description	relatedIdentifier
Software	Jakarta Messaging (version 3.1.0)		https://projects.eclipse.org/projects/ee4j.messaging
Software	JSON (version ISO/IEC 21778:2017)	Data format used to make requests and receive responses via the Databus and the RS Facade	https://www.iso.org/standard/71616.html
Software	JSON-LD (version 1.1)	Data format used for Search Service exports	https://www.w3.org/TR/json-ld/
Software	REST API (no version specified)	The RS Facade provides a REST API so that clients (such as the EOSC User Dashboard) can receive resource recommendations to display to the user.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Representational_state_transfer

9 Integration Options

There are three main scenarios for integrating other components with the EOSC-RS.

- The first scenario targets presentation (i.e UI) components of the EOSC ecosystem, which can get and utilise a set of recommended (and relevant) resources for a given user.
- The second scenario deals with the situation when the EOSC-RS capabilities are extended with a new recommendation engine. Such a recommendation engine can implement additional use cases that are not currently supported.
- Lastly, the third scenario relates to the way to add a new data source to be processed by EOSC-RS. A new source can be added to the existing catalogue of resources in order to improve the quality of the generated recommendation or extend the scope of the types of resources that can be recommended.

10 Interoperability Guidelines

There are many potential ways for integrating additional components into the EOSC-RS, such as external services or new internal modules that extend the existing functionality of the EOSC-RS. Table 10-1 below lists the entry points in the EOSC-RS, which make technical integration possible in general and the following scenarios in particular:

Scenario 1: adding a new client, i.e. a consumer of recommendations;

Scenario 2: adding a new recommendation engine;

Scenario 3: adding a new source of data.

Table 10-1: EOSC-RS integration points

Integration point	Type	References and comments
Databus - UserActions	Jakarta Messaging/JSON	Databus / User Actions
Databus - Marketplace domain events	Jakarta Messaging /JSON	Databus

Databus - Recommendations	Jakata Messaging /JSON	Databus
Search Service dumps format	JSON-LD	Search Service data schemas
SearchService API - listing dumps	REST/JSON	Search Service
S3/Ceph API - transferring dumps	AWS S3 compliant	Authorization is required. S3 cloud address: https://s3.cloud.cyfronet.pl Bucket name: ess-mock-dumps
RS Health checks API	REST/JSON	Monitoring of a deployed RS
RS Facade API	REST/JSON	RS facade

10.1 Scenario 1 – adding a new client

An external client wants to consume recommendations generated by EOSC-RS. Because the EOSC-RS does not provide any endpoints accessible from the public network, the new client must be in the same private network as the EOSC-RS. It must also integrate with two components, the RS Facade and the Databus.

Figure 10.1: integration points for a new EOSC-RS client

10.1.1 Integration with RS Facade

Integration with the RS Facade component allows a client to obtain various types of recommendations via its REST API. It is a component that aggregates all available recommendation engines into one consistent API. It also provides additional functionalities necessary for the proper operation of the EOSC-RS, including saving generated recommendations for subsequent evaluation.

In order to get recommendations for a specific user, the client sends a request to the RS Facade API containing all required fields and identifies itself by setting its CLIENT_NAME:

```
client_id:"{CLIENT_NAME}"
```

The detailed format of the interactions with the RS Façade connection points are provided in *Appendix A – RS Facade*.

10.1.2 Integration with the Databus

In order to obtain personalised recommendations, it is necessary to provide the EOSC-RS with information about the user, their behaviour and preferences. This information is obtained from the EOSC-RS via the Databus.

Any client presenting resources available in the EOSC-RS to the end user should publish messages regarding the user's interaction with those resources in the form of User Actions, especially when recommendations are presented along with the resources. These messages allow the EOSC-RS to create personalised recommendations consistent with the user's preferences. In addition, they supply the EOSC-RS with information about the popularity of a given resource, allowing it to provide suggestions for anonymous users and statistics for resource Providers. This is defined in detail in *Appendix B – Databus*.

10.2 Scenario 2: adding a new recommendation engine

Primarily EOSC-RS generates recommendations based on user activity in the EOSC Portal. User activities, such as selecting a specific dataset, generate User Action events. When collected and analysed, they describe users' behavioural patterns and consequently their profiles and interests.

The EOSC-RS can be extended with a new recommendation engine in order to implement extra use cases that are not currently provided by existing components.

There are two main steps followed when adding a new recommendation engine:

- Integration with data sources (databus, internal databases)
- Integration with the ES Facade via its API.

10.2.1 Step 1: Integration with data sources

The first step is to integrate with a data source, such as the Search Service, Databus or an internal database (see Figure 10.2).

The Search Service provides information about resources and training materials. The Databus allows a new recommender engine to consume User Action event messages, generated in real-time as user activities occur in the Marketplace and/or to publish messages (e.g. about recommendations generated). The internal databases of the EOSC-RS provide access to e.g. information about users and services.

Figure 10.2: integrating a new data source with the EOSC-RS

10.2.1.1 Information available from the Search Service

Resources from the EOSC Research Graph, specifically:

- Publications
- Datasets
- Software
- Other research products

Resources from the Marketplace:

- Services
- Data Sources

Resource from the EOSC Knowledge Hub:

- Training materials

10.2.1.2 Information available from the databus

- User actions
- User events

This is defined in detail in *Appendix B – Databus*.

10.2.1.3 Information available from internal databases

Some components in the EOSC-RS architecture have internal databases that can be exposed to other RS components (on a read-only basis).

For example, the 'RS-Mongo' database has information about:

- Marketplace services
- Marketplace users - both anonymous and authenticated (including their past user actions)

The information is periodically updated to keep in step with the Marketplace.

10.2.2 Step 2: Integration with the Facade

The second step is integration with the RS Facade via its REST API to expose the recommendations presented to a client, such as the Marketplace or the User Dashboard. This is defined in detail in *Appendix A – RS Facade*.

10.3 Evaluating a new integration

It is beneficial to evaluate the effectiveness of any integration with the EOSC-RS, in order to determine whether or not the overall User Experience has been improved as a result.

Suggested approaches are given below:

- Scenario 1: adding a new client, i.e. a consumer of recommendations: traditional methods, such as user workshops, to see obtain feedback on the new client.
- Scenario 2: adding a new recommendation engine: traditional methods, such as online A/B testing combined with instrumentation, to compare usage of the website with and without the new recommendation engine; use the Recommender Metrics Framework, in particular the dashboard, to compare the quality of recommendations given, before and after (assuming a baseline is available).
- Scenario 3: adding a new source of data: traditional methods, such as online A/B testing combined with instrumentation, to compare usage of the website with and without the data source; use the Recommender Metrics Framework, in particular the dashboard, to compare the quality of recommendations given, before and after (assuming a baseline is available).

11 Examples of solutions implementing this specification

11.1 Scenario 1 example

There are currently three clients using recommendations created by EOSC-RS and they are the EOSC Marketplace, Search Service and User Dashboard [4]. The way the Search Service has been integrated with the EOSC-RS is as follows:

- The Search Service makes a call to the RS Facade API, providing the whole request context. There are two scenarios:
 - get three recommendations for display in the recommendation panel.
 - sort N resources based on their relevance - for use by the 'sort by relevance' option.
- The EOSC-RS returns the IDs of the recommended/sorted resources and sends a message of type recommendations topic to the Databus.

- The Search Service identifies the relevant objects in its index, based on the IDs returned from the EOSC-RS and displays them either as recommendations or resources sorted by relevance.

11.2 Scenario 2 example

In the current version of the EOSC-RS, there are two recommendation engines. One provides recommendations based on user interactions with research outputs (such as publications, datasets, or software), the other based on interactions with services (including training materials).

11.3 Scenario 3 example

The example is the data set from the EOSC training catalogue, which has been recently added and processed by the EOSC-RS, which in turn makes it possible to recommend relevant training resources to users of the Marketplace, Search Service and User Dashboard.

12 Appendix A – RS Facade

The RS Facade is responsible for offering a consistent API for the entire EOSC Recommendation System. Its task is to mediate between the modules generating recommendations (Online AI/ML engine, Marketplace Recommender System) and external services (Search Service, User Dashboard). It divides its tasks between the individual recommendation modules, then collects the results, aggregates them, and performs re-ranking if necessary. In addition, it records the generated recommendations.

The GitHub repository containing the latest release can be found at [5] .

The general scheme of the operation of RS Facade is presented in Figure 12.1.

Figure 12.1: RS Facade general scheme of operation

12.1 RS Façade Endpoints

12.1.1 Recommendations endpoint

The recommendations endpoint is called to provide several sets of selected resources to be presented to a given user. Based on the context of the recommendation, the endpoint should return a list of lists of recommended items' IDs, obtained from the recommender agent. Each list could be used to prepare an independent recommendation panel. Along with recommended resources, the response contains corresponding explanations in long and short formats for each recommendation. Explanations contain details of the reasoning behind the recommendation of a given resource. Those explanations could be used as additional information in the assembled recommendation panel.

The RS Facade delegates request for recommendations regarding Services (for requests with panel_id set to the value "service" or "v1" or "v2") to the Marketplace Recommender System and all the rest to the Online AI/ML engine.

This endpoint allows the resource candidates provided in the candidates' field to be sorted. To sort candidates, the engine_version value should end with "sort"

Table 12-1: Recommendation context

<i>Field</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Optional</i>
user_id	The unique Marketplace identifier of the logged-in user.	Integer	yes
unique_id	The unique identifier of the not logged in user	String	
aai_uid	The unique AAI identifier of the logged user.	String	yes
timestamp	The exact time of the recommendation request sending	DateTime	
visit_id	The unique identifier of the user presence on the recommendation page at the specific time	String	
page_id	The unique identifier of the page with the recommendation panel	String	
panel_id	The unique identifier of the recommender panel on the page	String	
candidates	List of candidates for recommendation	Candidates	
search_data	Data specification	SearchData	
client_id	Client ID, possible values: marketplace, search_service, user_dashboard, undefined	String	yes
engine_version	Engine version	String	yes

Table 12-2: Recommendation candidates

<i>Field</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Optional</i>
dataset	List of resource ids of dataset candidates for sorting	List[String]	yes
publication	List of resource ids of publication candidates for sorting	List[String]	yes
software	List of resource ids of software candidates for sorting	List[String]	yes
other	List of resource ids of other research product candidates for sorting	List[String]	yes
training	List of resource ids of training candidates for sorting	List[String]	yes
service	List of resource ids of service candidates for sorting	List[String]	yes
datasource	List of resource ids of data source candidates for sorting	List[String]	yes

Table 12-3: Recommendation SearchData

<i>Field</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Optional</i>
q	Search phrase	String	yes
category_id	Category	List[String]	yes
geographical_availabilities	Countries	List[String]	yes
order_type	Order type	String	yes
providers	Provider	List[String]	yes
rating	Rating	String	yes
related_platforms	Related platforms	List[String]	yes

scientific_domains	Scientific domain	List[String]	yes
sort	Sort filter	String	yes
target_users	Target users	List[String]	yes

Table 12-4: Recommendation response

Field	Description	Type
panel_id	Name of the recommendation list	String
recommendations	List of recommended services' IDs	List[String]
explanations	List of explanations	List[String]
explanations_short	List of shortened explanations	List[String]
engine_versions	The internal engine that made recommendations	List[String]

12.1.2 Response from connected recommendation engines

The API of recommendation systems connected to the RS Facade (Online AI/ML engine and Marketplace Recommender System) should be exactly the same as above, but in the response, it should include the "score" field which determines the relevance of the resource. This field will be used for aggregation and re-ranking. The values of the "score" field should be in the range [0,1] where 1 means the most relevant resource, and 0 is the least relevant resource.

Table 12-5: RecommendationSet

Field	Description	Type
panel_id	Name of the recommendation list	String
recommendations	List of recommended services' IDs	List[String]
explanations	List of explanations	List[String]
explanations_short	List of shortened explanations	List[String]
scores	A score of the corresponding resource on the basis of which the choice of recommendation has been made	List[Float]
engine_version	The internal engine that made recommendations	String

Table 12-6: Databus message

Field	Description	Type
context	Recommendation context	RecommendationContext
panel_id	Name of the recommendation lists	String
recommendations	List of recommended services' IDs	List[String]
recommender_systems	List of recommendation systems	List[String]
sources	List of sources	List[Source]

Table 12-7: Recommendation source

<i>Field</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Type</i>
engine_version	The internal engine that made recommendations	String
panel_id	Name of the recommendation list	String
recommendations	List of recommended services' IDs	List[String]
recommender_system	Name of the recommendation system	String

12.1.3 Project completion endpoint

Based on the project given as input (as per Table 12-8), services that are frequently combined with the ones existing in the project are recommended.

Table 12-8: Project completion recommendation request

<i>Field</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Type</i>
project_id	The id of the project currently viewed by the user	int
num	Number of recommendations to be returned	int

The response is a list of dictionaries with fields, as shown in Table 12-9.

Table 12-9: Project completion recommendation response

<i>Field</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Type</i>
service_id	Service Id is the id of the recommended service	int
score	The score is the support from the frequent item sets	float

12.1.4 Similar services endpoint

Based on the service given as input (as per Table 12-10), similar services are recommended by utilizing both textual and metadata attributes.

Table 12-10: Similar services recommendation request

<i>Field</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Type</i>
user_id	The id of the user (as it was given in the marketplace)	int
service_id	The id of the service currently viewed by the user	int
num	Number of recommendations we want to be returned	int

The response is a list of dictionaries with fields, as shown in Table 12-11.

Table 12-11: Similar services recommendation response

<i>Field</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Type</i>
service_id	Service Id is the id of the recommended service	int
score	The score is the support from the frequent item sets	float

12.1.5 Similar resources endpoint

Endpoint used to obtain suggestions of similar EOSC Research Graph resources (datasets, publications, software, training materials, other_research_product) and training resources for a specified resource. A RecommendationSet is sent in response.

Table 12-12: Similar resource suggestion request

Field	Description	Type	Optional
user_id	The unique Marketplace identifier of the logged-in user.	Integer	yes
unique_id	The unique identifier of the not logged in user	String	
aai_uid	The unique AAI identifier of the logged user.	String	yes
timestamp	The exact time of the recommendation request sending	DateTime	
page_id	The unique identifier of the page with the recommendation panel	String	
panel_id	The unique identifier of the recommender panel on the page	String	
client_id	Client ID, possible values: marketplace, search_service, user_dashboard, undefined	String	yes
engine_version	Engine version	String	yes
resource_id	Resource unique identifier	String	
resource_type	Resource type one of: "datasets", "publications", "software", "trainings", "other_research_product"	String	

12.1.6 Databus messages

In order to calculate the quality of recommendations and to train models used in recommendation engines, the RS Facade logs requests for recommendations along with the responses. A message containing the complete request and response is sent to the Databus, as shown in Table 12-13.

Table 12-13: RS Facade databus message - recommendations received

Field	Description	Type
context	Recommendation context	RecommendationContext
panel_id	Name of the recommendation lists	String
recommendations	List of recommended services' IDs	List[String]
recommender_systems	List of recommendation systems	List[String]
sources	List of sources	List[Source]

The schema of the source object is shown in Table 12-14.

Table 12-14: RS Facade databus message – recommendation source details

Field	Description	Type
engine_version	The internal engine that made recommendations	String
panel_id	Name of the recommendation list	String

recommendations	List of recommended services' IDs	List[String]
recommender_system	Name of the recommendation system	String

12.1.7 Example of request body for commendations endpoint

```
{
  "user_id": 0,
  "unique_id": "string",
  "aai_uid": "string",
  "timestamp": "2023-05-31T12:41:17.070Z",
  "visit_id": "string",
  "page_id": "string",
  "panel_id": "all",
  "candidates": {
    "dataset": [],
    "publication": [],
    "software": [],
    "other": [],
    "training": [],
    "service": [],
    "datasource": []
  },
  "client_id": "marketplace",
  "engine_version": "string",
  "search_data": {
    "q": "string",
    "categories": [
      "string"
    ],
    "geographical_availabilities": [
      "string"
    ],
    "order_type": "string",
    "providers": [
      "string"
    ],
    "rating": "string",
    "related_platforms": [
      "string"
    ],
    "scientific_domains": [
      "string"
    ],
    "sort": "string",
    "target_users": [
      "string"
    ]
  ]
}
```

12.1.8 Example of request body for project completion endpoint:

```
{
  "project_id": 0,
  "num": 0
}
```

12.1.9 Example of request body for similar services endpoint:

```
{
  "user_id": 0,
  "service_id": 0,
  "num": 0
}
```

12.1.10 Example of request body for similar resources endpoint:

```
{
  "user_id": 0,
  "unique_id": "string",
  "aai_uid": "string",
  "timestamp": "2023-05-31T12:55:47.359Z",
  "page_id": "string",
  "panel_id": "string",
  "resource_id": "string",
  "resource_type": "datasets",
  "client_id": "marketplace",
  "engine_version": "string"
}
```

13 Appendix B – Databus

The Databus is used for asynchronous communication between the EOSC-RS and other EOSC components.

13.1 Databus messages

13.1.1 Marketplace database events

Topic: mp_db_events

Messages published on this topic relate to all activities on the Marketplace database.

Examples:

13.1.1.1 Create new user

```
"{"cud":"create","model":"User","record":{"id":2956,"scientific_domains":[]
,"categories":[],"accessed_services":[]},"timestamp":"2022-08-
17T14:19:33Z"}"
```

13.1.1.2 Update user

```
"{"cud":"update","model":"User","record":{"id":2956,"scientific_domains":[2
7],"categories":[3],"accessed_services":[]},"timestamp":"2022-08-
17T14:20:07Z"}"
```

```
{"cud":"update","model":"Provider","record":{"id":55,"name":"100 Percent IT"},"timestamp":"2022-08-17T14:28:07Z"} " "
```

13.1.1.3 Update service

```
{"cud":"update","model":"Service","record":{"id":485,"name":"3DBionotes-WS","description":"The web platform 3DBionotes-WS integrates multiple Web Services and an interactive Web Viewer to provide a unified environment in which biological annotations can be analyzed in their structural context.\n\nCurrent sources of information include post-translational modifications, genomic variations associated to diseases, short linear motifs, immune epitopes sites, disordered regions and domain families.\n\nSince the COVID-19 outbreak, new structural data from many viral proteins have been incorporated in a new 3DBionotes-COVID-19 section.","tagline":"3DBIONOTES-WS a web application designed to automatically annotate biochemical and biomedical information onto structural models.","countries":["WW"],"order_type":"fully_open_access","rating":"0.0","status":"published","categories":[36,62,99,100,142,187,94],"providers":[235,305,315],"resource_organisation":235,"scientific_domains":[21],"platforms":[],"target_users":[1],"access_modes":[1612],"access_types":[1607],"trls":[1590],"life_cycle_statuses":[1599],"required_services":[],"related_services":[]},"timestamp":"2022-08-17T14:29:48Z"} " "
```

13.1.1.4 Update ScientificDomain

```
{"cud":"update","model":"ScientificDomain","record":{"id":38,"name":"Medical \u0026amp; Health Sciences EDITED"},"timestamp":"2022-08-17T14:31:31Z"} " "
```

13.2 Recommendations

The RS Facade sends messages to the Databus containing information about each request for recommendations (the query) and response (details of recommendations received from each recommendation engine).

Table 13-1: Recommendations message sent by RS Facade to Databus

Field	Description	Type
context	Recommendation context	RecommendationContext
panel_id	Name of the recommendation lists	String
recommendations	List of recommended services' IDs	List[String]
recommender_systems	List of recommendation systems	List[String]
sources	List of sources	List[Source]

Table 13-2: Recommendation Context

Field	Description	Type	Optional
user_id	The unique Marketplace identifier of the logged-in user.	Integer	yes
unique_id	The unique identifier of the not logged in user	String	
aai_uid	The unique AAI identifier of the logged user.	String	yes
timestamp	The exact time of the recommendation request sending	DateTime	
visit_id	The unique identifier of the user presence on the recommendation page in the specific time	String	

page_id	The unique identifier of the page with recommendation panel	String	
panel_id	The unique identifier of the recommender panel on the page	String	
candidates	List of candidates for recommendation	Candidates	
search_data	Data specification	SearchData	
client_id	Client ID, possible values: marketplace, search_service, user_dashboard, undefined	String	yes
engine_version	Engine version	String	yes

Table 13-3: Recommendation source

Field	Description	Type
engine_version	The internal engine that made recommendations	String
panel_id	Name of the recommendation list	String
recommendations	List of recommended services' IDs	List[String]
recommender_system	Name of the recommendation system	String

13.2.1 Examples

For a query for one resource type:

```
{
  "context": {
    "aai_uid": null,
    "candidates": {},
    "client_id": null,
    "engine_version": null,
    "page_id": "1",
    "panel_id": "datasets",
    "search_data": "q=None categories=None
geographical_availabilities=None order_type=None providers=None rating=None
related_platforms=None scientific_domains=None sort=None
target_users=None",
    "timestamp": "2013-02-24 12:28:45.610000+00:00",
    "unique_id": "8",
    "user_id": 8,
    "visit_id": "1"
  },
  "panel_id": "datasets",
  "recommendations": [
    "50|doi_dedup___:3f85968efdba03445968718fdb1a5a0a",
    "50|doi_dedup___:b5e060aa8dcf9c230e9882dffc4f7f2b",
    "50|doi_dedup___:cf23c1a6f6e5106fbc176314719f9986"
  ],
  "recommender_systems": [
    "Online_engine"
  ]
}
```

For a query for all resource types:

```
{
  "context": {
```

```

    "aai_uid": null,
    "candidates": {},
    "client_id": null,
    "engine_version": null,
    "page_id": "1",
    "panel_id": "other_research_product",
    "search_data": "q=None categories=None
geographical_availabilities=None order_type=None providers=None rating=None
related_platforms=None scientific_domains=None sort=None
target_users=None",
    "timestamp": "2013-02-24 12:28:45.610000+00:00",
    "unique_id": "8",
    "user_id": 8,
    "visit_id": "1"
  },
  "panel_id": "all",
  "recommendations": [
    "50|doi_dedup___:b12342173a4a7cbc05c06b8dbc6948eb",
    "50|doi_dedup___:3f85968efdba03445968718fdb1a5a0a",
    "18",
    "50|doi_dedup___:91ad02e5bab43dc306fc7e684d0c52be",
    "50|od_____3532::c80beb8d9a7a744ea53960809a10fa17",
    "50|doi_dedup___:331d6a88b69ef85d3d66c690c3c6d65e",
    "50|doi_dedup___:b5e060aa8dcf9c230e9882dfc4f7f2b",
    "50|doi_____:75afea8e815bceebf07391e4ba3e41e7",
    "50|doi_____:aaf38ac8899e4ec4456dac117d3aa92e",
    "21"
  ],
  "recommender_systems": [
    "Online_engine"
  ],
  "sources": [
    {
      "engine_version": "content_visit",
      "panel_id": "publications",
      "recommendations": [
        "50|doi_dedup___:b12342173a4a7cbc05c06b8dbc6948eb",
        "50|doi_dedup___:331d6a88b69ef85d3d66c690c3c6d65e",
        "50|doi_dedup___:2155ca3f1d0c951db3179943f33ee443"
      ],
      "recommender_system": "Online_engine"
    },
    {
      "engine_version": "content_visit",
      "panel_id": "datasets",
      "recommendations": [
        "50|doi_dedup___:3f85968efdba03445968718fdb1a5a0a",
        "50|doi_dedup___:b5e060aa8dcf9c230e9882dfc4f7f2b",
        "50|doi_dedup___:cf23c1a6f6e5106fbc176314719f9986"
      ],
      "recommender_system": "Online_engine"
    },
    {
      "engine_version": "content_visit",
      "panel_id": "trainings",
      "recommendations": [
        "18",
        "21",
        "2"
      ],
      "recommender_system": "Online_engine"
    }
  ]

```

```

    },
    {
      "engine_version": "content_visit",
      "panel_id": "software",
      "recommendations": [
        "50|doi_dedup___:91ad02e5bab43dc306fc7e684d0c52be",
        "50|doi_____:75afea8e815bceebf07391e4ba3e41e7",
        "50|doi_____:d47393c013ecf381b5af5507b7b9b62d"
      ],
      "recommender_system": "Online_engine"
    },
    {
      "engine_version": "content_visit",
      "panel_id": "other_research_product",
      "recommendations": [
        "50|od_____3532::c80beb8d9a7a744ea53960809a10fa17",
        "50|doi_____:aaf38ac8899e4ec4456dac117d3aa92e",
        "50|doi_____:caed31b29a75ff85689b703976ba24fc"
      ],
      "recommender_system": "Online_engine"
    }
  ]
}

```

Example from Marketplace Recommender

```

{
  "recommender_system": "cyfronet",
  "context": {
    "user_id": 1,
    "unique_id": "5642c351-80fe-44cf-b606-304f2f338122",
    "client_id": "marketplace",
    "timestamp": "2022-11-21T13:59:51.488Z",
    "visit_id": "202090a4-de4c-4230-acba-6e2931d9e37c",
    "page_id": "/services",
    "panel_id": "v1",
    "engine_version": "NCF",
    "candidates": [
      1,
      2,
      3,
      4
    ],
    "search_data": {
      "q": "",
      "categories": [
        1,
        2,
        3
      ],
      "geographical_availabilities": [
        "WW"
      ],
      "order_type": "open_access",
      "providers": [
        1,
        2,
        3
      ],
      "rating": "5",
      "related_platforms": [
        1,

```

```

    2,
    3
  ],
  "scientific_domains": [
    1,
    2,
    3
  ],
  "sort": "_score",
  "target_users": [
    1,
    2,
    3
  ]
}
},
"response": {
  "panel_id": "v1",
  "recommendations": [
    1,
    4,
    2
  ],
  "explanations": [
    "This service has been selected based on historical orders of the
given user and similar orders of similar users",
    "This service has been selected based on historical orders of the
given user and similar orders of similar users",
    "This service has been selected based on historical orders of the
given user and similar orders of similar users"
  ],
  "explanations_short": [
    "This service has been selected based on historical orders.",
    "This service has been selected based on historical orders.",
    "This service has been selected based on historical orders."
  ],
  "scores": [
    0.9999943971633911,
    0.9999229907989502,
    0.9265388250350952
  ],
  "engine_version": "NCF"
}
}

```

References

- [1] Hienola, A., Shepherdson, J.W. et al. D5.2a EOSC Front-Office requirements analysis. EOSC Tech. rep. (2022)
- [2] Knijnenburg, B.P., Willemsen, M.C., Gantner, Z. et al. Explaining the user experience of recommender systems. *User Model User-Adap Inter* 22, 441–504 (2012). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11257-011-9118-4>
- [3] Opensource.org 2023. Open Source Initiative Approved Licenses. [online] Available at <https://opensource.org/licenses/>
- [4] Eosc-portal.eu. 2023. EOSC Marketplace. [online] Available at: <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/>
- [5] Psn.pl 2023. EOSC RS Façade. [online] Available at <https://git.man.poznan.pl/stash/projects/EOSC-RS/repos/rs-facade/browse>